

CURE MONITORING OF CFRP: ELECTRICAL IMPEDANCE ANALYSIS

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1 Introduction

Optimization of composite materials properties is linked to process optimization [1, 2]. As far as thermoset matrix are concerned, the cure monitoring, including a real-time adjustment of the process parameters, may be appropriate for the purpose. The use of an instrumentation embedded in the heart of the composite could answer to this issue [3]. Furthermore, this instrumentation could be let inside the structure to ensure not only an in-service monitoring (SHM) but also a functionalization of the composite material itself.

Different strategies are encountered: sensors used on or inside materials but also the material itself used as a sensor. Sensors can be used to measure mechanical, thermal, rheological, electrical... parameters [4-7]. During the curing process through, electrical parameters are frequently measured thanks dielectrical [8, 9] or resistance approaches [10, 11]. But those rarely propose the use of the same sensors for SHM purpose.

The present paper deals with the upstream phase of a study aiming at showing the capability to monitor the electrical impedance of T700/M21 composites from its manufacture phase to the end of its life cycle (SHM). The material is used here as a sensor. A specific instrumentation was developed to ensure accurate electrical impedance measurements in its heart. It consists in thin flexible electrodes embedded in the manufactured composites.

The preliminary results show good agreement between rheological (viscosity, complex shear modulus, degree of cure) and electrical (capacity and resistance) measurements during the cure cycle. The paper presents the material, the developed approach and the analysis of the current results.

2 Material and cure cycle

Unidirectional composite samples made from Hexcel T700/M21 carbon/epoxy prepegs (used in aeronautics and the space industry) are studied here. The thickness retained is 2 mm (corresponding to 8 T700/M21 prepreg plies, each 256 μm thick).

The resistivity of the T700 carbon fibre [12] is around $10^{-5} \Omega\cdot\text{m}$ in the range [-100 °C, 150 °C]. M21 polymer is an insulator and the frequency evolution of its conductivity with temperature presented two distinct conduction states [12] (Fig. 1). At low frequency, a resistive conduction can be distinguished, regardless of the frequency, and corresponding to extremely high resistivities. In the worst case, at 150 °C, minimal resistivity is about $10^{10} \Omega\cdot\text{m}$, fifteen times greater than the resistivity in the fibre. When increasing the frequency the electrical conduction becomes capacitive.

In summary, in a T700/M21 laminate, direct current flows only along the fibres and via the inter-fibre contact points (percolation points). The higher the fibre rate, the lower will be the resistance value. In the same way, the high-frequency capacitive conduction will enable the inter-fibre capacitive conduction (via the resin) to be quantified, so as to extract the capacitance sensitive to the matrix and voids volume fractions.

In this study, we are seeking to demonstrate that it is feasible to monitor the curing process. Curing was therefore carried out in an oven without pressure and with a thermal cycle composed of an isothermal phase of 120 °C min at 180 °C and with temperature rise and fall rates of 2 °C/min (cure cycle recommended by the manufacturer).

3 Experimental protocol

This electrical impedance measurement calls for the insertion of electrodes, limiting parasitic access elements (series and contact interface resistance or parasitic parallel capacity) by means of correct dimensioning and judicious positioning, in order to achieve reliable readings. To this end, we propose the use of flexible printed circuits. These are made of a 50 μm thick polyimide film (good compatibility with the M21 resin) and a 35 μm thick copper/gold-metallized band.

The choice of this flexible type of connector takes into account the strain parameters of the cure cycle, but also reflects the need for an electrode that is sufficiently deformable to be able to adapt to the mechanical strains at the heart of the material. The low thickness and nature of these electrodes means that they can be inserted between plies of the laminates, without affecting the structure produced. In this study, surface-interface flexible electrodes of 0.5cm² were used. These flexible electrodes will be termed “flex” in the rest of this article.

Three flex were placed transversally to the fibres to measure the vertical and diagonal conductions through the thickness and were inserted between plies 1 and 2 and between plies 7 and 8 of 100 mm x 100 mm samples as described in Fig. 2. Thanks to these flex inserted directly in the heart of the composite, 4- and 2-wire measurements give the same value of the composite resistance. The global access resistance (electrode/fibre interface and feed wire) was less than 1 Ω which is negligible compared to the composite resistance (over 250 Ω). 2-wire measurements were thus undertaken using a Hioki IM3570 impedance analyser.

This method of embedding the sensor in the heart of the material enables sensitive measurements to be taken of both resistance and capacity, corresponding to the standard electric model. The changes in of these measured quantities during the cure cycle can then be correlated with standard rheological parameters.

A frequency sweep of the sinusoidal voltage (from 10 Hz to 100 kHz), at constant amplitude, combined with a measurement of the alternating current (amplitude and phase), enables the frequency evolution of the complex electrical impedance (Z) of

the model to be established. As shown in the following equation, at low frequency, the conduction is essentially resistive ($Z \approx R_p$) and at high frequency the impedance becomes mostly capacitive ($Z \approx 1/C_p \cdot \omega$). This enables the values of R_p and C_p to be extracted.

$$Z = \frac{R_p}{1 + jR_p C_p \omega} \quad (1)$$

Where : R_p is the resistance; C_p the capacitance; f the frequency; ω the angular velocity ($\omega = 2\pi f$).

From these measurements, the values of the resistance R_p measured at 10Hz and that of the capacitance C_p measured at 100 kHz were extracted for the purpose.

Knowledge of the sequencing of the different mechanisms interacting during the curing process makes it possible to predict the evolution of the electrical impedance during manufacturing. From a theoretical point of view, for a solid material, the electrical resistance depends on geometrical and material parameters. In this case, the geometrical parameter will correspond to the zone covering the length of the power lines.

The resistance depends on the direction of the fibres, on the fibres volume fraction and on the percolation points between fibres, which will be constantly changing during the cure cycle. Fibre displacement during the viscous, liquid phase favours the creation of percolation points and should induce a collapse in the resistance value. From the liquid/gel transition to the solidification of the resin, this mechanism remains present, but with much slower kinetics. Finally, solidification (cross-linking) and the state of internal strains (residual thermal strains, among others), will immobilize the extension zone of the current.

To all this can be added the dependence of the resistivity on temperature (resistivity of the fibres and percolation points). As regards the capacitance of an insulating material, this is also defined by geometrical and material parameters (2).

$$C = \varepsilon \times \frac{S}{e} \quad (2)$$

where: S is the inter-fibres effective area ; e is the average inter-fibres distance and ε the average value of the dielectric permittivity of the resin and porosities.

As with the resistance R_p , the geometric parameters (S and e) and dielectric permittivity ε , will evolve during the curing process [13]. The capacitance C_p will thus depend on the arrangement of the network of fibres during curing and on changes in the properties of the resin (resin rate, cross-linking and porosity rates).

Before any measurements, a calibration (Fig. 3) was required to determine the inductive effects (self-series, marked L_s), the resistive effects (series resistance of wires, marked R_s) created by the length of the feed wires, which were about 5 metres long and the capacitive effects (parasitic capacitance caused by wire coupling, marked $C_{parasitic}$). The short-circuit impedance measurement gives the values of the access series resistance ($R_s = 0.7 \Omega$) and the series inductance ($L_s < 200$ nH). The open-circuit impedance enables to measure the leakage resistance of the electrical access ($R_{Leakage} > 350$ M Ω) and the parasitic capacitance ($C_{parasitic} = 40$ pF). So, those values obtained made it possible to guarantee a measurement precision of better than 1% for R_p resistances in the range [100 Ω , 5 M Ω] and for C_p capacitances ranging from 500 pF to 100 μ F.

A thermocouple was inserted into the heart of the composite to follow the changes in of the curing temperature inside the material and to compare it to the recommended temperature.

4 Rheological tests and results

In order to analyze these electrical results and correlate them with the different phase changes of the material, we compared them to the rheological study curves obtained experimentally on a parallel plate rheometer (Thermofisher) and on DSC (T.A. Instruments) [14].

Rheological analysis enables the following parameters to be measured:

- the dynamic viscosity, μ ;
- the conservation or elastic modulus, G' ;
- the dissipation or viscous modulus, G'' ;

- the loss tangent, $\tan(\delta) = \frac{G''}{G'}$;
- the degree of cure, α .

As described in Fig. 4 four specific zones of interest (Z. 1 to Z. 4) and twelve characteristic points are highlighted. The first zone (Z. 1) corresponds to the heating up phase of the cycle. The point at which the resin fluidified was passed (marked P_{Tgi}) is characterized by a change in the slope of μ . This point and the following ones are determined by the method of tangents. The curves of the rheological parameters exhibit other inflection points and minimal points that we can retain for this study:

- $\tan(\delta)_{\min,1}$: first minimum point of $\tan(\delta)$;
- PG''_1 : the first inflection point of G'' ;
- PG''_{\min} : minimum point of G'' ;
- $\tan(\delta)_{\min,2}$: second minimum point of $\tan(\delta)$;
- $\tan(\delta)_1$: the first inflection point of $\tan(\delta)$.

In the second zone (Z. 2) the resin passed from a viscous, liquid state into that of an elastic gel. This phase change corresponds to a strong increase in the viscosity (μ), and in the elastic (G') and viscous (G'') moduli leading to a $\tan(\delta)$ peak corresponding to the gel point (marked P_G). The cross-linking phase of the resin begins from this point. The two inflection point of G'' and $\tan(\delta)$ (respectively marked PG''_2 and $\tan(\delta)_2$) are considered as points of interest for the present study.

The last phase change (Z. 3) shows the vitrification point (P_V), where the resin passes from an elastic gel to a vitreous, viscoelastic solid. At this stage, the glass transition temperature of the M21 matrix reaches the curing temperature. A modification in the reaction kinetics can then be observed. It is no longer catalytic, but continues by diffusion. The manifestation of this modification appears as a rise in G' and μ , as well as a peak in G'' and $\tan(\delta)$. Finally it leads to a plateau corresponding to the end of the crosslinking (point marked P_F). The third inflection point of G'' (marked PG''_3) is considered as another point of interest here.

In the last zone (Z. 4) rheological parameters remain constant.

Presentation of the characteristic points is given here at the moment of arrival at the isotherm,

obtained by readings of the thermocouple embedded in the laminate. This “time to isotherm” is considered as a zero reference of time, so as to take account of possible variations during a specific curing cycle.

5 Electrical impedance results

Measurements of R_p and C_p presented here were obtained in the vertical direction (index v) and diagonally (index d). In order to refine the correlation/detection of characteristic points, an analysis was also made of the evolution of absolute discrete time derivatives $|R_p'|$ and $|C_p'|$ plotted in logarithmic scale. The results are split up into the four previous zones (Z. 1 to Z. 4) and two additive zones corresponding to the cooling down (marked Z. 5 and to Z. 6) on Fig. 5 and Fig. 6. All the corresponding measured characteristic points are summarized and compared to the rheological results in Tab. 1.

During the first phase (Z. 1) sensors enter correctly into contact with the plies of the prepreg and exhibit the maximal values of $|R_p'|$ and $|C_p'|$. After that, R_p shows a rapid reduction: ever closer contact with the fibres (intimate sensor/fibre contact in the fibre planes and via the percolation points) in a resin undergoing liquefaction. At the same time, a first major peak in C_p is observed: the first major change in the viscosity of the resin, the liquefaction phase. In this zone, the following points of interest are found:

- $\tan(\delta)_{\min,1}$: both maxima of $|R_p'|$ and $|C_p'|$;
- $PTgi$: initial inflexions of R_p and C_p ;
- $\tan(\delta)_1$: maximum of C_p and end of the linear decrease of $|R_p'|$;
- PG''_1 : inflection point following the maximum of C_p and beginning of the linear behaviour of R_p ($|R_p'|$ quasi-constant);
- $\tan(\delta)_{\min,2}$ and PG''_{\min} : local rise of C_p between its two major peaks; end of the linear part of R_p ($\tan(\delta)_{\min,2}$) and inflection point that follows the linear part and begins a new behaviour of R_p (PG''_{\min});

The second zone (Z. 2) corresponds to a much slower decrease in R_p : rearrangement of the fibre/sensor contacts in a progressively hardening resin which tends to push the material resistance

towards its final value [15]. A second major peak of C_p is also present: the second significant change in the viscosity of the resin, and the first phase of cross-linking (before vitrification). In this second zone, the following points of interest are found:

- $\tan(\delta)_2$ and PG''_2 : second peak of C_p ;
- P_G : inflection point following the second peak of C_p and point of return to a rapid decrease in R_p .

However, R_p also shows sensitivity to the cure cycle (unlike the capacitance). The passage from the rise to the thermal plateau affects it particularly, which presents a jump (increase) in the transition zone.

The third phase (Z. 3) exhibits a homogenous decrease in C_p and R_p . The detected characteristic points are:

- PG''_3 : inflection point of C_p ;
- P_V : inflection point of R_p ;
- P_F : break of slope of $|R_p'|$.

Here C_p is sensitive to the change in the cross-linking rate, but not to the kinetics of the processes underway, engendering a growing state of internal strain. These same strains will improve the sensor/fibre contact and enable the resistance to be sensitive to the vitrification phase.

The zone 4 (Z. 4) presents a constant value for $|R_p'|$, meaning that there is a fixed contact between sensors and fibres.

Zone 5 (Z. 5) shows a linear decrease in C_p ($|C_p'|$ constant) until the end of the cure cycle, but $|R_p'|$ decreases and increases. This last phenomenon could be explained by the appearance of residual strains at the heart of the material (rise in conductivity) during the cooling down period, and by the fall in temperature (rise in resistivity). Thermal strains may have a greater effect during cooling, leading to a drop in C_p . Then, after that, the process would be reversed. Residual strains are in place and the thermal effect of the cooling becomes stronger, leading to an increase in C_p .

The last zone (Z. 6) corresponds to the cooling down of the material after the door of the oven is opened. C_p decreases and R_p increases, both more strongly, again demonstrating their thermal sensitivity.

The obtained results highlight the value of the proposed protocol and demonstrate that, with the aid of these sensors, complete automation of the manufacturing process of composite structures is feasible (optimization of the curing cycle by real-time automatic control). R_p and C_p measurements can thus be used to define simple phenomenological and more complex multi-physics laws to address this issue. This is the main objective of studies underway. We will focus on α , μ and G'' . Behaviour of G' is indeed directly linked to the one of μ [16] and $\tan(\delta)$ to G'' and G' .

As described in Fig. 7, $1/R_p$ can be used to define the thermal transition between the dynamic mode and isothermal mode behaviours of α . Furthermore two specific laws could be defined to link α and $1/R_p$ before and after the gel point, PG . For μ and G'' , global laws can't be defined as easily as for α . For example, local laws should be defined for each phase transition using the corresponding characteristic points.

A first 3-D modelization of the electrical conduction throughout the material is also currently undertaken. The longitudinal and transverse conduction is presently studied in the case of a **one** ply UD T700/M21 cured on a specific substrate enabling embedding up to 15 flex. First results expose a weak measurement capability of the instrumentation in the longitudinal direction of the fibres (Fig. 8) because of a low-value R_p (0.6 Ω) and the non-linearity of C_p depending on frequency. R_p and C_p would be accurately measured within a ply using a transverse conduction in the spectral range [1 kHz, 10 kHz] where they remains constant and of significant values (resp. 1800 Ω and 280 pF).

The functionalization of the material as a temperature or strain sensor can thus be considered. Measurements of R_p (in the longitudinal but mainly in the transverse conduction) and C_p (in the transverse conduction) exhibit a good accuracy and linear behaviours with temperature (Fig. 9). Fig. 10 shows changes in strain sensitivity in longitudinal and transverse conduction. Only transverse conduction can be used for strain measurements: C_p measurements show higher response rates (145%, in compressive and 563%, in tensile strains) than the ones obtained for R_p (resp. 2.3% and 8.5%).

6 Conclusion and perspectives

In the course of this study, a simple and robust instrumentation has been developed using flexible electrodes designed to conduct an impedance-metric analysis at the heart of a T700/M21 UD carbon material used here as a sensor. By using flexible printed circuits (flex) and the associated acquisition system, it was possible to monitor the evolution of the behaviour of this material during its cure cycle in an oven. The evolution over time of the measured electrical parameters, R_p and C_p , matches the evolution of the rheological parameters studied by standard methods. Up to twelve points of agreement were established with the variation in viscosity, dynamic shear moduli, the loss tangent and the degree of cure. This instrumentation exposes also a good temperature and strain sensitivity.

It thus appears possible to fit a composite material with this instrumentation and to use it not only to monitor the curing method, but, better still, to control it. By modeling the rheological parameters, and equally the physical (fibre/resin and porosity rates) and thermal parameters through electrical impedance-metric values, it should be possible to establish in real time the appropriate moments for stopping, modulating or correcting the cure cycle.

In addition, according to where the electrodes are placed, the information obtained can be viewed as homogenized (direction longitudinal to the fibres) or localized (direction transverse to the fibres). Thus, the material could be qualified either in a global way, or from a more discriminating point of view, so as to identify specific defects. In manufacturing, incidents during layup or curing can, for example, cause errors in the matrix/fibre or voids volume fractions, or even structural defects (delamination, imperfect ply-drop etc.).

Looking beyond the manufacturing stage, electrodes at the heart of the material can also act as monitors of the health of the composite material during the conditioning stage and the service stage (SHM and functionalization of the material). A second type of modelling will be required to evaluate changes in the physicochemical and mechanical parameters that will come with aging or damage to the material.

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Fig. 1. Evolution of the conductivity of RTM6 resin with temperature (from -150°C to 150°C in steps of 10°C) [12]

Fig. 2. Insertion of flexes and schematized path of current lines for vertical (flexes 1 and 2) and diagonal measurement (flexes 2 and 3) according to the longitudinal orientation

Fig. 3. Calibration of the acquisition system: a- Short-circuit; b- Open circuit

Fig. 4. Rheological characteristic points retained for the study

Fig. 5. Analysis of measurements of Rp

Fig. 6. Analysis of measurements of Cp

Fig. 7. Correlation between α et R_p

Fig. 8. Spectral impedance measurements longitudinally (left) and transversally to the fibres (right)

Fig. 9. Temperature effect in the range [-50°C; 150°C]

Fig. 10. Strain effect

Points	Impedance measurements			Rheological measurements		Zones
	Time to isotherm (mn)	Temperature (°C)	Obtention	Time to isotherm (mn)	Temperature (°C)	
$\tan(\delta)_{\min,1}$	-64.5	54.5	C_p and R_p	-68.5	48.5	1
P_{Tgi}	-50.5	81.5	C_p and R_p	-48	82	
$\tan(\delta)_1$	-41	100	C_p and R_p	-42.5	95	
PG''_1	-37.5	106.5	C_p and R_p	-38	102	
$\tan(\delta)_{\min,2}$	-18	145	C_p and R_p	-15	150	
PG''_{\min}	-10.5	160	C_p and R_p	-13	155	
$\tan(\delta)_2$ or PG''_2	+5	180	C_p	+5	180	2
P_G	+11	180	C_p and R_p	+11	180	3
PG''_3	+32	180	C_p	+31.5	180	
P_V	+51	180	R_p	+51	180	
P_F	+103	180	R_p	+106	180	

Tab. 1. Characteristic points of phase changes for the T700/M21 obtained by rheological tests